

Cilosari: a new rice variety released in Indonesia through cross hybridization of the mutant line with IR36

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We irradiated seeds of variety Seratus Malam with different doses of gamma rays (10, 20, 30, and 40 krad) in 1983. The M₂ generation plants were selected for semidwarf stature, and from 50,000 M₂ plants, 130 semidwarf mutants were

selected. A semidwarf mutant, SM-268 /PsJ, selected from the 20-krad treatment, was used for analysis of allelic relationship. In the allelic test, semidwarf mutant SM-268/PsJ was crossed with IR36. However, in the F₃ an early maturity line Obs-1647/PsJ was selected and tested for yield potential in the F₁₀ generation. The agronomic characters of Obs-1647/PsJ and the mother varieties are in Table 1.

Based on yield trials at 27 locations during 1992-95, Obs-1647/PsJ showed a higher yield potential at several loca-

tions when compared with IR64 (Table 2). The Ministry of Agriculture in Indonesia released this line in July 1996 as Cilosari, a variety for irrigated areas. ■

Table 1. Agronomic characters of Obs-1647/PsJ (Cilosari) and mother varieties IR36 and SM-268/PsJ.

Character	Parent 1 SM-268/PsJ (mutant)	Parent 2 IR36	Derived line Obs1647/PsJ (Cilosari)
Plant height (cm)	60-65	70-80	110-125
Maturity (d)	110-115	110-120	110-120
Productive tillers (no.)	5-7	14-19	10-15
1,000 grain weight (g)	15-17	23-25	26-27
Amylose content (%)	22-23	24-25	20.5-21.0
Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	2.0-2.5	4.0-4.5	5.0-6.5
Cooking and eating quality	Not good	Medium	Good
Resistance to BPH biotypes 1 and 2	Susceptible	Resistant	Resistant
Resistant to bacterial leaf blight	Susceptible	Resistant	Resistant

Table 2. Mean yield of Cilosari in yield trials at 27 locations. 1992-95.^a

Location	1992-93 wet season		1993 dry season		1993-94 wet season		1994-95 wet season	
	Cilosari	IR64	Cilosari	IR64	Cilosari	IR64	Cilosari	IR64
Madiun	5.70 a	5.20 a	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lamongan	5.23 a	5.17 a	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ponorogo	8.40 a	8.30 a	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bekasi	7.30 a	5.90 b	-	-	-	-	-	-
Tulungagung	8.10 a	7.80 a	-	-	-	-	-	-
Probolinggo	7.10 a	5.60 b	-	-	-	-	-	-
West Sumatera	4.90 a	6.40 b	-	-	-	-	-	-
Yogyakarta	-	-	5.99 a	4.37 a	-	-	-	-
Banyuwangi	-	-	4.58 a	4.20 a	-	-	-	-
Jombang	-	-	5.01 a	5.33 a	-	-	-	-
Ponorogo	-	-	5.45 a	5.94 a	-	-	-	-
Serang	-	-	3.69 a	3.63 a	-	-	-	-
Temanggung	-	-	4.92 a	5.38 a	-	-	-	-
Ogankomering	-	-	-	-	6.47 a	6.43 a	-	-
North Aceh	-	-	-	-	6.55 a	5.73 a	-	-
Central Lampung	-	-	-	-	8.46 a	8.02 a	-	-
Bandung	-	-	-	-	10.14 a	9.68 a	-	-
South Sulawesi	-	-	-	-	5.82 a	5.07 a	-	-
South Lampung	-	-	-	-	7.04 a	5.50 b	-	-
Bandung	-	-	-	-	-	-	9.97 a	9.68 a
West Aceh	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.63 a	2.65 b
Indragiri Hilir	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.71 a	2.42 b
Tanjung Jabung	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.65 a	4.45 b
Kerinci	-	-	-	-	-	-	6.83 a	5.67 b
Bengkalis	-	-	-	-	-	-	4.76 a	2.55 b

^aIn a row in the same location, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by HSD test at the 5% level.

FARO 44 and FARO 50: two irrigated lowland rice varieties for Nigeria

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Irrigated lowland rice is grown on around 10% of the 1.77 million ha planted to rice in Nigeria. In August 1996, the National Crop Variety Release Committee in Nigeria released two semidwarf varieties, FARO 44 and FARO 50, for this ecosystem. They are suitable for all the zones except southeastern Nigeria, where African rice gall midge (ARGM) is a major problem. Their detailed characteristics are shown in the table.

FARO 44 is the varietal name given to the line SI-692033. It was bred at Chiayi Agricultural Experiment

Agronomic characteristics of two lowland rice varieties.

Characteristic	FARO 44	FARO 55
Designation	Sipi 692033	ITA230
Cross	Sipi 661044/ Sipi 651020	BG90-2 ⁴ / Tetep
Days to 50% flowering	85	90
Plant height (cm)	105	110
Blast resistance ^a	3	1
ARGM ^a	9	9
RYMV ^a	9	9
Iron toxicity ^a	7	7
Leaf scald ^a	3	1
Brown rice length (mm)	6.9	7.3
Brown rice width (mm)	2.2	2.2
L/W	3.1	3.3
Grain type	Long slender	Long slender
Chalkiness ^a	0	5
Gel temperature ^a	7	5
Amylose %	26.0	28.0
Husk color	Straw	Straw
1000-grain weight (g)	26.5	23.6
Av yield (t ha ⁻¹)	4.0	5.0
Yield potential (t ha ⁻¹)	8.0	10.0

^aSES scale, IIRRI (1996).